
Special issue

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Universidade Federal de Pelotas,
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do Sul

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Communication & Society

ISSN 0214-0039

E ISSN 2386-7876

www.communication-society.com

2026 – Vol. 39 (1)

pp. 435-444

How to cite this article:

Salaverría, R., Graves, L., & Recuero, R. (2026). Crowdsourced validation is not fact-checking: Understanding the difference, *Communication & Society*, 39(1), 435-444 <https://doi.org/10.15581/003.39.1.029>

Crowdsourced validation is not fact-checking: Understanding the difference

Few recent platform policies have drawn as much scrutiny as Meta's 2025 decision to, in CEO Mark Zuckerberg's words, "get rid of fact-checkers and replace them with Community Notes, similar to X, starting in the US" (Kaplan, 2025). Announced just two weeks before Donald Trump's return to the White House, the policy change raises important unresolved questions for scholars as well as policymakers and fact-checkers themselves.

Among fact-checkers, the move to end US fact-checking partnerships came as the latest and largest step in an ongoing "platform retreat" (Holan, 2025b) characterized by diminished financial, institutional and technological support from platform companies for fact-checking and for anti-disinformation efforts generally (Holan, 2025a; Hernández-Echevarría, 2025). Since its launch in late 2016, Meta's Third-Party Fact-Checking program grew into arguably the single most important source of funding for fact-checkers worldwide, driving tremendous growth across the field and accounting for 45 percent of revenues to members of the International Fact-Checking Network in recent years (IFCN, 2025b, 2026). The possibility that—as many fact-checkers still expect—the Meta partnerships will be phased out around the world further threatens the field's sustainability at a moment of declining support from foundations, technology firms and the public sector. In the most recent IFCN survey, three-quarters of member organizations described their finances "as vulnerable or in crisis" (IFCN, 2026).

Beyond financing, Meta's embrace of crowdsourced Community Notes raises difficult questions about fact-checking's model of impact, centered on the platform alliances that have profoundly shaped the field's mission over the last decade (Graves et al., 2024; Cazzamatta, 2025). Meta's partnerships covering Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Threads have offered both a privileged view of online mis- and disinformation on those networks, and a form of direct influence on the algorithmic systems governing them (Ananny, 2018; Bélair-Gagnon et al., 2023; Farkas & Bengtsson, 2026). Similarly, TikTok's internal moderation teams flag, restrict and sometimes delete posts based on inputs from the work of its 20 independent fact-checking partners worldwide (TikTok, n.d.). Fact-checkers have been quick to point to statistics Meta itself used to advertise to demonstrate the scale and impact of the program, for instance showing that 95 percent of viewers do not click through to see a post with a fact-checking label (EFCSN, 2025). What kind of direct impact can fact-checking have on social media if platform alliances continue to erode? It is worth remembering that Twitter was piloting a program to bring professional fact-checkers into its crowdsourced Birdwatch platform—which became X's Community Notes—before Elon Musk bought the network in 2022 (Mantas, 2021).

TikTok continues to work with fact-checking partners but is testing its own crowdsourced moderation system, called Footnotes (Lindner & Maheshwari, 2025).

For academic researchers, the shift “from fact-checking to community notes” invites inquiry along several distinct threads that cross disciplinary lines. A short list of large open questions includes, for example, the implications for platform governance and regulation at the state and transnational levels; the evolution of fact-checking organizations, practices, and institutions as platform priorities change; and the actual dynamics and effectiveness of moderation systems that integrate crowdsourced, professional and AI verification in different ways and to different degrees. The articles in this Special Issue of *Communication and Society* touch on these themes from different regional, disciplinary, and methodological perspectives.

In this introductory Editorial, we would like to raise a more basic question that returns to the original formulation Zuckerberg offered: what, exactly, are fact-checkers being “replaced” by as Meta and other platforms move to Community Notes? If the essence of what professional fact-checking organizations do is verification—AFP, which operates the largest fact-checking platform in the world, calls it simply “verifying content that has already been published” (AFP, n.d.)—is that also a reasonable description of the crowdsourced, algorithmically governed exchanges at the center of Community Notes? While public and academic discourse often describes Community Notes as “crowdsourced fact-checking” (Godel et al., 2021) or “community-based fact-checking” (Chuai et al., 2026), it is worth noting that X’s official literature does not use the term. In the following paragraphs, we develop a subtle but important distinction, between *verification* and *validation*, as a conceptual wedge for scholars navigating this emerging fault line in anti-disinformation research and practice.

1. From professional fact-checking to crowdsourced validation

The transition from professional fact-checking toward distributed models of collaborative validation does not merely constitute a technical change in content moderation tools. Rather, it represents a deeper transformation in the epistemological architecture of digital platforms. What is at stake is not only who debunks disinformation, but who holds the legitimacy to publicly determine what can be considered reliable information in increasingly fragmented communicative environments (Borenstein et al., 2025).

Over the last decade, professional fact-checking has become established globally as an institutional response to the deterioration of the digital information ecosystem (Graves and Lauer, 2020). In a context marked by the acceleration of content circulation, the loss of authority of news media, and the very crisis of the concept of truth (McIntyre, 2018), intensified recently by the rise of artificial intelligence (Shin, 2026; Palese, 2026), fact-checking organizations have instituted themselves as trusted intermediaries, capable of providing standardized verification procedures, methodological transparency, and accountability. The international growth over more than a decade of initiatives such as PolitiFact (US), Full Fact (UK), Chequeado (Argentina), or Maldita (Spain), to mention only a few, has led to the consolidation of a new journalistic genre, even a culture, centered on the public assessment of claims (Graves, 2016).

However, the exponential growth in the volume of content distributed on social media, much of it deliberately false, has revealed the structural limits of this model. The almost artisanal logic of fact-checking—based on largely manual review, labor-intensive documentary verification, and relatively slow editorial production—clashes with the speed and scale at which digital platforms disseminate content, privileging velocity, virality, and mass interaction. Although fact-checkers themselves constitute one of the most innovative forms of journalistic organization (Valero Pastor et al., 2026) and are characterized precisely by proactively exploring

AI tools to detect false multimodal content (Larraz & Salaverría, 2026), their response capacity ultimately falls short of the magnitude of the challenge posed by information manipulation online.

Indeed, disinformation no longer circulates as clearly false, standalone pieces that can be straightforwardly “debunked.” Instead, it increasingly appears as a swarm of falsehoods—what have come to be called “disinformation narratives” (Suau & Puertas-Graell, 2023) or, in the words of Kaja Kallas, the EU High Representative for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, “deceptive narratives” (EEAS, March 2025, p. 2)—in which continuous flows of ambiguous, decontextualized, and emotionally polarizing content intersect in the service of hidden interests. In this scenario, the capacity of professional verifiers to intervene is unquestionably limited, both in scale and in time. Ultimately, it reproduces the age-old struggle between David and Goliath.

The transition toward collaborative validation systems responds, at least in part, to this scalability crisis. Contrary to their previous claims, digital platforms have recently begun to argue that no professionalized body of fact-checkers can singlehandedly oversee the volume of information produced and shared daily by hundreds of millions of users. To justify his decision to shut down the third-party fact-checking program in the US, Zuckerberg claimed the effort produced “too many mistakes,” arguing that “fact-checkers have been too politically biased” and have “destroyed more trust than they created” (Thompson, 2025). Fact-checkers have vocally disputed those claims, often citing Meta’s earlier praise for the partnership (EFCSN, 2025; IFCN, 2025a).

In response to this alleged deviation by fact-checking organizations, platforms now claim that the solution lies in assigning part of the task of contextualization and correction to user communities themselves, supported by algorithmic models capable of aggregating collective signals of credibility, usefulness, or reliability.

This shift entails a significant mutation in the governance of public truth. Whereas traditional fact-checking rested on relatively consolidated journalistic principles—professional expertise, documentary verification, and editorial independence (Mena, 2019)—collaborative models transfer part of that authority to forms of distributed participation mediated by algorithms. The central question ceases to be merely what is true and becomes, additionally, how consensus over truth is socially constructed within highly polarized digital platforms (Waisbord, 2018).

In this regard, crowdsourced validation systems such as Community Notes represent a noteworthy hybrid model, positively assessed by fact-checkers themselves (Maldita, 2025), yet one about which doubts remain regarding its ability to function autonomously. Collective annotation does not entirely eliminate traditional verification logic, but it does reconfigure it within an architecture in which users, algorithms, and platforms share evaluative functions. Platforms do not directly verify content; rather, they design the conditions under which certain users may contextualize claims and other users collectively validate that contextualization. In other words, platforms establish the algorithmic rules that determine what qualifies as truth or, at least, what is worthy of remaining visible online. This model blurs—or even eliminates—the role of experts, since trustworthiness is no longer granted to those who master a discipline but becomes a customary process susceptible to manipulation.

The underlying question, therefore, is whether this collective validation process results in more authentic and trustworthy content. The first empirical evidence, including that presented in this Special Issue, reveals that the coexistence of different verification and validation models produces far more complex phenomena than might initially be imagined. A recent study

published in *Nature Communications* on the efficiency of “community-based fact-checking”, for instance, found that exposing users to community notes reduces the subsequent spread of misleading posts by an average of 61.2% (Chuai et al., 2026). This is a positive side-effect. Likewise, another study on the coexistence of professional fact-checking and community notes revealed that the latter recurrently cite fact-checking sources (Borenstein et al., 2025); that is, contributors rely heavily on information previously verified by professional fact-checkers, who continue to be recognized as authoritative sources. A third experimental study with 1,810 US citizens, conducted by Drolsbach et al. (2024), showed that community notes are perceived as more reliable than simple disinformation labels for users across all the political spectrum. This greater trust stems primarily from the context and explanatory verification they provide, rather than from special trust in those who write them. As such, professional fact-checking and crowdsourced validation appear to be moving toward increasingly intertwined formulas.

These transformations are embedded within a broader context of growing “platformization” of information governance (Gillespie, 2018). Technology platforms have progressively shifted from centralized moderation and content removal to more decentralized models based on contextual labeling, algorithmic reduction of visibility, or community oversight. Rather than directly assuming the role of referees of truth, platforms seek to present themselves as neutral infrastructures that facilitate collective evaluation processes. However, this apparent decentralization does not necessarily imply a disappearance of platform power. On the contrary, algorithm design and participation rules continue to be defined within opaque corporate structures.

For this reason, the transition from professional fact-checking to collaborative validation should not be interpreted as a straightforward democratization of information control. A more critical view reminds us that it is also a strategic redistribution of responsibilities: platforms partially externalize the political and reputational costs of moderation onto user communities, while retaining control over the technical architecture that organizes visibility, circulation, and legitimization of corrections. The launch of Community Notes on X in December 2022 and Meta’s subsequent decision to imitate this model (Meta, March 13, 2025) reflect this evolution. Moderation no longer depends exclusively on alliances with external fact-checking organizations but instead relies on systems of reputation, distributed evaluation, and cross-ideological consensus.

All of this suggests, as Bartsch et al. (2025) argue, that we are entering a new stage of the digital information ecosystem characterized by the coexistence of different models of epistemic authority: professional experts, collective intelligence, and algorithmic reputation. Rather than fully replacing traditional fact-checking, collaborative systems appear to function as complementary mechanisms that expand detection and contextualization capacity, while also introducing new vulnerabilities related to polarization, participatory inequality, and algorithmic opacity.

2. Defining crowdsourced validation

Just as it has been necessary in recent years to establish a conceptual distinction between mal-, mis-, and disinformation (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017, p. 5), a new terminological and conceptual need now emerges: distinguishing between professional fact-checking and crowdsourced validation. As we have explained, these are closely related and often intertwined realities, but with distinct characteristics and foundations.

With origins in journalistic practices dating back to the twentieth century in outlets such as *The New Yorker*, fact-checking has been consolidated in the early decades of the twenty-first

century as an institutionalized practice of public verification (Graves, 2016). As a qualified variant of journalism, its activity consists of a systematic process of checking claims, whose veracity is contrasted through documentary information, consultation with expert sources, and the use of rigorous methodologies. From this standardized and transparent method of verification—akin to a form of informational forensic investigation,—professional fact-checkers adopt the role of notaries of public information.

Fact-checking organizations operate across all five continents, and their workers share a “shared belief in [their] ability to determine the objective truth of claims, which is validated by evidence and a transparent process of reproducibility or modeling the fact-checking process” (Koliska & Roberts, 2025, p. 500). Although initially linked to political journalism, fact-checking has progressively expanded into areas such as health, science, and international conflicts. The consolidation of professional standards in this journalistic activity has been significantly supported by initiatives such as the International Fact-Checking Network (IFCN), founded in the US in 2015, and the European Fact-Checking Standards Network (EFCSN), active since 2023, both of which have helped disseminate solid operational and ethical principles internationally.

Paradoxically, the growing public relevance of fact-checking has also been fueled by its most vocal detractors. The strategic use by major powers and other international actors of large-scale mechanisms of information manipulation and deliberate falsification—commonly referred to as Foreign Information Manipulation and Interference (FIMI)—has turned fact-checking into a priority for various international institutions, even as it has been proscribed by others. In 2026, while the European Commission considers fact-checking a “crucial pillar of the EU approach to information manipulation and foreign interference” (European Commission, 2026), in the US the Trump administration (2025–2029) has acted to weaken and punish third-party fact-checkers and content moderators, arguing that their actions amount to censorship of American voices (Luscombe, 2025).

Within this context of professional normalization of fact-checking, either as an activity carried out by independent organizations or as a specialty integrated into large media corporations, broader forms of distributed verification have emerged. Whereas professional fact-checking generally involves specialized organizations, standardized methodologies, editorial oversight, and formalized ethical codes, emerging collaborative models rely on the participation of users—who are not necessarily experts or first-hand witnesses—to collectively detect, contextualize, or evaluate questionable content.

It is in this context that the concept of “crowdsourced fact-checking” (Godel et al., 2021), collaborative verification, or “community-based fact-checking” (Chuai et al., 2026) arises. This term refers to systems in which large groups of users participate in information evaluation tasks through distributed mechanisms of signaling, rating, or contextualization. Its theoretical foundation lies in the idea of the “wisdom of crowds” (Surowiecki, 2004), according to which a sufficiently diverse aggregation of individual contributions can yield reliable judgments, even when participants lack professional expertise.

The concept of crowdsourced validation also often includes a community moderation component, which is absent from professional fact-checking. When this occurs, systems function as general mechanisms of social regulation of content. Community moderation may involve little more than reputational labeling, usefulness voting, or reporting behaviors, without necessarily entailing factual verification of claims. This is why we believe it is more accurate to refer to this practice as “crowdsourced validation” rather than “crowdsourced fact-checking”.

In the specific case of Community Notes, the system simultaneously combines several dimensions: collective sources, distributed moderation, collaborative contextualization, and

algorithmic governance. The notes used by platforms such as X or Meta no longer function as categorical journalistic verifications, but instead add context or interpretative clarifications rather than delivering conclusive debunkings. This turns the system into a hybrid form of contextual correction—merely indicative—where the boundary between verification and moderation becomes blurred. To put it briefly, it's a “validation” system.

From this perspective, the evolution from professional fact-checking to collaborative systems does not merely represent a technical innovation, but a conceptual redefinition of how informational authority is constructed, distributed and —yes— validated, in the contemporary digital environment.

3. Challenges and tensions

As suggested earlier, Meta's abrupt pivot away from fact-checking was only the latest sign of the dissolution of the international anti-disinformation ecosystem that took shape after 2016. That ecosystem centered on an elite consensus, which peaked during the Covid pandemic, that brought into alignment diverse institutional actors including fact-checking organizations, technology companies, academic researchers, and state authorities (especially security and public health agencies). The fracturing of that wider elite consensus—what Zuckerberg glossed as “a cultural tipping point” toward free expression (Kaplan, 2025)—highlights an epistemological tension also reflected in the move to “community-based” moderation.

Here again, the distinction between verification and validation sheds useful light. Verification has its root in the Latin *verus*, or truth, and centers on the idea of dispositive evidence or proof: To verify is to show something to be true or accurate. Though often used as a synonym in everyday language, validation connotes a less restrictive basis for approval. It derives from the Latin *validus*, or strong; to be valid is to be well-founded, applicable or acceptable by some relevant standard. This underlying difference between professional verification and crowdsourced validation plays out across several overlapping dimensions.

Reproducibility: Professional fact-checking aspires to replicability, in that a standardized method applied to a given claim should yield a consistent verdict. While a debate exists about how reliably fact-checkers achieve this in practice (e.g., Lim, 2018; Markowitz et al., 2023), their published methodologies and their accreditation by standards bodies such as the IFCN and EFCSN reflect and enact independent reproducibility as the basis for durable truth claims. In contrast, crowdsourced validation makes no express claim to replicability. To what extent outcomes are path dependent remains an open question, but a comment's strength is collective approval, reflecting algorithmic “bridging” thresholds applied across individualized judgments of “usefulness” that may or may not include weighing of sources and evidence as well as language, tone, apparent ideology, and etc.

Transparency: The claim to replicability in fact-checking rests on a commitment to transparency: about procedures for selecting and evaluating claims in general, and about the specific sources and reasoning behind each individual judgment. As in science, this makes evidence and methods not only visible but contestable, facilitating a wider discourse that sometimes results in revised conclusions or refined procedures. As implemented in Community Notes, crowdsourced validation offers a powerful but very different kind of transparency. Publishing the governing algorithm and the dataset of notes and ratings has fueled a rich vein of research on the large-scale dynamics of the validation platform, including assessments of its effectiveness vis-a-vis professional fact-checking. However, understanding how the crowdsourcing algorithm works at scale does not explain why specific notes are shown or suppressed. It does not offer reasons in the epistemological sense.

Evidence: Professional fact-checking centers on the collection, evaluation and presentation of diverse sources of evidence. Published fact-checks typically take the form of simple narratives describing that research process, with established conventions for discussing sources with differing degrees of reliability and more or less relevance to the question. Crowdsourced community notes sometimes cite authoritative evidence (including, often, professional fact-checks) and this plays some role in their validation, at least in the aggregate. But, even under the most generous assumptions about what drives ratings of Community Notes, what they are *not* is tightly structured vehicles for identifying dispositive evidence and translating it into a decisive factual judgment.

Authority: Considering methods and evidence leads to the difficult question of authority. Professional fact-checking draws heavily on the authority of institutionally validated sources of expertise and data in the public world: official statistics, credentialed experts, peer-reviewed research, and so on. This counts as a kind of validation—but validation on the basis of credentialing and evaluation systems intended precisely to codify the production of reliable knowledge, however imperfectly. As developed above, Community Notes grounds authority generally in the idea of the “wisdom of crowds,” and specifically in cross-partisan consensus as an index of “useful context.”

Seen in light of these epistemological considerations, the anti-disinformation ecosystem that is now fracturing was more than a coalition of institutional actors. With professional fact-checking at its center, it acted as an architecture for translating verification across multiple contexts—public discourse, algorithmic systems, academic research, public policy, etc.—according to broadly shared standards of evidence, method, and accountability. The decision by digital platforms to replace professional fact-checking with a model of crowdsourced validation adds new uncertainties and risks to the digital ecosystem, where ensuring the integrity of information has always been problematic.

4. Future research agenda

This evolution calls for new areas of research that move beyond the extensive scholarship on fact-checking accumulated over the past decade. Fact-checking has received sustained scholarly attention in recent years. Now, however, validation processes and their broader consequences demand closer examination. Our Special Issue already includes valuable contributions in this direction, and empirical studies assessing the effects of this transformation are beginning to emerge. Still, our understanding of the phenomenon remains limited, and much remains to be explored (Salaverría & Cardoso, 2023).

Research on crowdsourced validation may also require methodological approaches that differ from those traditionally employed in fact-checking studies. The shift introduces a renewed challenge for research on algorithmic transparency. Earlier studies mainly focused on identifying the criteria platforms use to amplify or suppress content. A different question now becomes increasingly relevant: how platforms select and prioritize the voices involved in collective validation processes. This challenge is further intensified by the increasing difficulty of accessing platform data and the circulation of this data. Understanding these mechanisms will be essential for assessing the democratic implications and epistemic reliability of these emerging systems.

Several additional questions also deserve attention. Crowdsourced validation systems may be vulnerable to coordinated manipulation campaigns or dynamics of polarization. This creates the need for further research on moderation and governance mechanisms. Comparative perspectives are equally important. Validation practices are likely to vary across political and

cultural contexts, making cross-national and cross-platform analyses increasingly relevant. At the same time, the growing delegation of validation tasks to users and communities may produce participation fatigue or new inequalities that remain largely understudied.

Given this context, understanding the shifts between verification and validation also requires a deeper study of how disinformation itself adapts within platformed and algorithmic ecosystems. As platforms continuously modify their affordances, recommendation systems, moderation policies, and visibility logics, they require constant adaptation of both validation and verification strategies.

Finally, the questions presented in this Special Issue underline how this is necessarily an ongoing field of study that requires continuous scrutiny and methodological adaptation. These emerging challenges ultimately reinforce the central argument of this editorial: crowdsourced validation is not fact-checking. Recognizing the difference is essential for conceptual clarity. It is also necessary for developing research agendas capable of understanding the transformations currently reshaping the contemporary information ecosystem.

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